

Potentiometric Studies on Some Ternary Complexes of Praseodymium(III) with Nitrilotriacetic Acid, N-Hydroxyethylethylenediaminetriacetic Acid and Ethylenediaminetetraacetic Acid as Primary Ligands

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The formation constants of the ternary complexes of Praseodymium(III) with Nitrilotriacetic acid (NTA), N-Hydroxyethylethylenediaminetriacetic acid (HEDTA) and Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) as primary ligands and Picolinic acid (PA) and Nitroso-R-salt (NRS) as secondary ligands have been investigated by potentiometric titration technique. The values of formation constants of 1:1:1 ternary chelates are reported at three different temperatures and at fixed ionic strength, $\mu=0.2M$ (NaClO_4). Stepwise stoichiometric formation constants for the binary complexes of Pr(III) with PA and NRS have also been determined under identical conditions. The values of $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ have been found in the order, $\log K_{MAL}^{NTA} > \log K_{MAL}^{HEDTA} > \log K_{MAL}^{EDTA}$. Trends in the formation constants are discussed. The data also indicates that the Pr(III) ion expands its co-ordination number larger than six in some of these species.

RECENTLY there has been considerable interest in the study of the mixed-ligand systems by pH-metric method¹⁻⁵. In continuation with our earlier work^{6,7}, on the application of Irving-Rossotti titration technique⁸ for the study of the ternary complexes of Pr(III), the results obtained on the study of the systems MAL, where M=Pr(III), A=Nitrilotriacetic acid (NTA) or N-Hydroxyethylethylenediaminetriacetic acid (HEDTA) or Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) and L=Picolinic acid (PA) or Nitroso-R-salt (NRS) are presented in this paper. The formation constants, $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$, have been determined at three different temperatures and at ionic strength, $\mu=0.2M$ (NaClO_4).

The necessary conditions for the study of ternary complexes by the present method is that the 1:1 (metal: primary ligand), MA, complex formation should be complete at low pH and metal-primary ligand complex (MA) should be stable at higher pH where the combination of secondary ligand (L) with MA takes place. The above condition holds good in the present systems. The mixed-ligand formation constant can be computed from the equation (1):

$$K_{MAL}^{MA} = \frac{[MAL]}{[MA][L]} \quad \dots (1)$$

Secondary ligands were chosen on the basis that the stability of secondary ligand complex (ML_1) should be quite less than that of the primary complex. So

that, three should not be any possibility of replacement reactions such as: $\text{MA} + \text{L} = \text{ML} + \text{A}$. Though, the stoichiometric stability constants of Pr(III)-PA complexes are reported earlier⁹, at 25° and at $\mu=0.1M$ (KNO_3), in order to compare the values of K_{MAL}^{MA} with K_{ML_1} under the identical conditions, the binary complexes (ML) have also been studied. The values of K_{ML} obtained for Pr(III)-NRS system at three different temperatures using Irving-Rossotti titration technique are reported in this paper for the first time. Recently, the rare-earth ions^{10,11} are considered to expand their co-ordination number larger than six. The assumption of co-ordination number of seven or eight for Pr(III), seems to explain the experimental observations more satisfactorily than a co-ordination number of six in case of [Pr(III)-(HEDTA)(L)] and [Pr(III)-(EDTA)(L)] systems as reported in this paper.

Experimental

Materials: A stock solution of 0.02M of $\text{PrCl}_3 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Indian Rare Earths Ltd.) was prepared in calculated quantity of perchloric acid and its metal content was estimated by spectrophotometric method¹². A stock solution of 0.02M PA (Sigma Chemical Co.) and 0.02M NRS (E. Merck, Germany) were prepared in doubly distilled water and were standardized potentiometrically.

Carbonate free 1.0M sodium hydroxide (E. Merck) was prepared and was standardized

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potentiometrically against potassium hydrogen phthalate. 1.0M sodium perchlorate (Neutral) and 0.1M perchloric acid was prepared by dissolving their AnalaR samples in doubly distilled water.

Apparatus : An expanded scale pH-meter with accuracy ± 0.02 pH units, supplied by the Electronic Corporation of India with a glass-calomel electrode assembly was used. The saturated calomel electrode was connected to the cell externally by means of an agar-agar bridge, saturated with KNO_3 , to prevent the formation of chloro-complexes. The design of the cell was such that it allowed flushing of nitrogen through the solution and also enabled measurements to be carried out in an atmosphere of nitrogen. The temperature was maintained by immersing the cell in an ultra thermostat bath (U-10, East Germany) having an accuracy of $\pm 0.1^\circ$.

Procedure : For the study of binary complexes the following three mixtures were prepared :

(a) $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ perchloric acid.

(b) $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ perchloric acid
+ $5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ ligand solution.

(c) $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ perchloric acid
+ $5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ ligand solution.
+ $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ Pr(III) solution.

The concentrations of common ingredients were kept identical in each mixture. The ratio between metal and ligand was kept 1 : 5. An appropriate amount of neutral sodium perchlorate solution was added to maintain the ionic strength 0.2M and the total volume of the mixtures were kept 100 ml in each case. These mixtures were titrated with 1.008M NaOH using pH-meter. In a graph of pH against volume of NaOH, the titration curves were referred as (A) acid titration curve (B) ligand titration curve and (C) complex titration curve. A typical plot of pH against volume of NaOH have been represented in Fig. 1 for PA and in Fig. 2 for NRS at 35° . The nature of the curves are similar at other temperatures also.

Fig. 1. Titration curves for Pr(III)-PA system at 35° at $\mu = 0.2M$

Curve (A) Acid titration curve.
(B) Ligand titration curve.
(C) Complex titration curve.

Fig. 2. Titration curves for Pr(III)-NRS system at 35° at $\mu = 0.2M$

Curve (A) Acid titration curve.
(B) Ligand titration curve.
(C) Complex titration curve.

For the study of ternary complexes following four mixtures were prepared.

- (A) $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ perchloric acid.
- (B) $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ perchloric acid
+ $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ secondary ligand.
- (C) $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ perchloric acid
+ $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ primary ligand
+ $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ Pr(III) solution.
- (D) $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ perchloric acid
+ $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ primary ligand
+ $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ Pr(III) solution
+ $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ secondary ligand.

In each case total volume was made up to 100 ml and ionic strength was maintained to $0.2M$ by

adding appropriate amount of neutral sodium perchlorate solution. In each case the ratio between metal, primary ligand and secondary ligand was kept 1 : 1 : 1. These mixtures were titrated against standard NaOH ($1.008 M$) using pH-meter. All titrations were carried out in nitrogen atmosphere at three different temperatures. The four titration curves obtained were referred as (A) acid titration curve, (B) secondary ligand titration curve, (C) primary complex titration curve and (D) ternary complex titration curve. A typical plot of pH against volume of NaOH have been represented in Fig. 3 for [Pr(III)-(NTA)(PA)] and in Fig. 4 for [Pr(III)-(HEDTA)(PA)] system. The nature of the curves for the systems [Pr(III)-(EDTA)(PA)] is similar as that for [Pr(III)-(HEDTA)(PA)]. The nature of curves are also similar for NRS ternary systems.

Fig. 3. Titration curves for Pr(III) (NTA)(PA) system at 25° at $\mu=0.2M$

- Curve (A) Acid titration curve.
- (B) Secondary ligand titration curve.
- (C) Primary complex titration curve.
- (D) Ternary complex titration curve.

Fig. 4. Titration curves for [Pr(III)-(HEDTA)(PA)] system.

- Curve (A) Acid titration curve.
- (B) Secondary ligand titration curve.
- (C) Primary complex titration curve.
- (D) Ternary complex titration curve.

Results

Proton-ligand Stability Constants : In the present work the values of 'practical' proton-ligand stability constants of PA and NRS (secondary ligands) have been evaluated at three different temperatures by calculating \bar{n}_A at various pH from the acid and ligand titration curves as reported earlier^{1,3}. The formation curves (\bar{n}_A against pH) for the proton-ligand systems are found to be extended between 0 to 1 on \bar{n}_A scale. Thus, the dissociation of HPA and HNRS can be represented as follows :

Two computational methods (A) interpolation at half \bar{n}_A values and (B) interpolation at various \bar{n}_A values were used for evaluation of proton-ligand stability constant values. The values obtained for 'practical' proton-ligand stability constants are tabulated in Table 1.

These values of protonation constants have been taken into account for the calculation of the formation constants of binary and ternary complexes.

Metal-ligand Stability Constants (K_{ML}) of Binary Complexes

The stoichiometry (1 : 3) of PA and NRS complexes with trivalent rare-earths has already been studied^{6,14} establishing the bidentate nature of these ligands. The titration curves (Fig. 1) of PA with Pr(III) shows that the metal curve (C) joins up with the ligand curve (B) indicating the dissociation of complex. The ligand curve (B) and metal curve (C) overlap in the region of the dissociation of complex. The hydrolysis of the metal ions results

in the liberation of extra protons and again the metal curve (C) diverges from ligand curve (B). Precipitation was observed at $\text{pH} \approx 7.5$ in case of PA and at $\text{pH} \approx 8.5$ in case of NRS. Hence, only that portion of titration curves where precipitation was not observed was used for calculations of \bar{n} values.

In the present case the formation constants (K_{ML}) for binary complexes of PA and NRS have been obtained by plotting \bar{n} against pL by the method of Irving-Rossotti. The formation curves drawn between \bar{n} and pL for the complexes formed by Pr(III) with PA and NRS are found to be extended between 0 to 3 in the \bar{n} scale indicating 1 : 3 (M : L) complex formation. A typical plot of \bar{n} against pL in case of PA is represented in Fig. 5. The nature of curves is similar for NRS system also. The metal-ligand stability constants were obtained from the analysis of metal-ligand formation curves (\bar{n} vs pL) using the method : (A) interpolation at half \bar{n} value and (B) interpolation at various \bar{n} values. In both the cases from the shape of the formation curves, it is apparent that stepwise formation of complexes is not independent. Hence, the values of $\log K_2$ have been calculated by the method of least squares (C).

The values of $\log K_1$ (± 0.03), $\log K_2$ and $\log K_3$ (± 0.05) for the complexes formed by Pr(III) with PA and NRS at various temperatures are summarised in Table 1.

Stability Constant of Ternary Complexes

The formation of ternary complex was concluded initially from qualitative evidence. The pH of the precipitation of mixed-ligand system was more than the pH of precipitation in the single ligand systems.

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF SOME Pr(III) COMPLEXES AT $\mu=0.2 M$ (NaClO₄)

System	Constant	Temperature								
		25°			35°			45°		
		A	Method B	C	A	Method B	C	A	Method B	C
H-PA	$\log K^H$	5.30	5.31	—	5.21	5.23	—	5.07	5.08	—
H-NRS	$\log K^H$	6.90	6.87	—	6.76	6.76	—	6.62	6.62	—
Pr(III)-PA	$\log K_1$	3.94	3.91	—	3.82	3.84	—	3.74	3.70	—
	$\log K_2$	3.13	3.10	3.12	3.04	3.01	3.05	2.98	2.97	2.98
	$\log K_3$	2.67	2.67	—	2.61	2.63	—	2.50	2.56	—
Pr(III)-NRS	$\log K_1$	4.29	4.31	—	4.25	4.27	—	4.20	4.22	—
	$\log K_2$	2.86	2.84	2.86	2.79	2.83	2.80	2.74	2.70	2.73
	$\log K_3$	2.59	2.61	—	2.53	2.50	—	2.42	2.41	—
Pr(III)-(NTA)(PA)	$\log K_{MAL}^{NTA}$	3.24	3.28	—	3.19	3.17	—	3.09	3.08	—
Pr(III)-(HEDTA)(PA)	$\log K_{MAL}^{HEDTA}$	3.24	3.22	—	3.16	3.15	—	3.09	3.06	—
Pr(III)-(EDTA)(PA)	$\log K_{MAL}^{EDTA}$	3.13	3.11	—	3.08	3.11	—	3.06	3.07	—
Pr(III)-(NTA)(NRS)	$\log K_{MAL}^{NTA}$	2.98	2.96	—	2.93	2.90	—	2.88	2.86	—
Pr(III)-(HEDTA)(NRS)	$\log K_{MAL}^{HEDTA}$	2.94	2.95	—	2.87	2.89	—	2.85	2.85	—
Pr(III)-(EDTA)(NRS)	$\log K_{MAL}^{EDTA}$	3.16	3.05	—	3.05	3.03	—	2.97	2.97	—

Further evidence was provided by comparing the ternary complex titration curve (curve D in Figs. 3, 4) with the composite curve (not shown in Fig.). The composite curve was drawn theoretically by the graphical addition of 1 : 1 MA curve of the titration curve for the free ligand (L). If there is any interaction between MA and L the composite curve should be displaced from the experimental curve (D). It was observed that for each mixed-ligand system the composite curve was located on the left-hand side of the experimental curve (D) in the pH range 4.5 to 9.0. The nature of the complex equilibrium whether stepwise or simultaneous was investigated according to the method suggested by Carey and Martell¹¹.

Fig. 5. Formation curves for Pr(III)-PA system at three different temperatures and at $\mu=0.2M$

—○—○—○—25°
 —△—△—△—35°
 —●—●—●—45°

Finally in order to characterize definitely the reaction occurring in the lower buffer region as to the formation of $M(A)_2$ and MAL_2 a potentiometric titration was performed employing the exact stoichiometric amounts of metal ion and ligands, capable of forming just the two postulated chelate species with no excess ligand. The resulting curve for 1 : 2 molar ratio of M : A and 1 : 1 : 2 molar ratio M : A : L respectively were found identical with curves for 1 : 1, M : A and 1 : 1 : 1, M : A : L. Thus, the possibility of formation of either 1 : 2 : 1 or 1 : 1 : 2 mixed-ligand chelate is completely ruled out.

It is observed from curve (C) of Fig. 3 and Fig. 4 that MA is formed at lower pH. It undergoes hydroxocomplex formation at higher pH. The curve (D) separates from (C) after pH 4.5 showing positive

values for $(V_3 - V_2)$, where V_3 is horizontal distance between curve (D) and curve (C) and V_2 is horizontal distance between curve (B) and curve (A) indicating that MAL formation takes place after the complete formation of 1 : 1 MA complex. In this range hydroxocomplex formation does not take place. The horizontal distance (V_2) between curve (A) and curve (B) can be measured and subtracted from the horizontal distance (V_3) between curve (C) and curve (D), where $(V_3 - V_2)$ corresponds to the amount of secondary ligand which gets bound with MA and so \bar{n} and pL can be calculated using equation :

$$\bar{n} = \frac{(V_3 - V_2)(N + E^0)}{(V^0 + V_1) \bar{n}_A T_{CL}^0}$$

where, V^0 is the initial volume of each mixture, V_1 is the volume of NaOH required in titration of mixture (A), T_{CL}^0 is concentration of (MA) which is equal to the total concentration of metal in mixture (D). The other terms have their usual meanings. pL values can be calculated using equation :

$$pL = \log \left[\frac{1 + \beta'H + \beta_2(H^+)^2}{T_{CL}^0 - \bar{n}T_{CM}^0} \frac{V^0 + V_3}{V^0} \right]$$

The values \bar{n} and pL were calculated at various pH values. A typical plot of \bar{n} against pL for [Pr(III)-(NTA)(PA)] system is shown in Fig. 6 and for [Pr(III)-(HEDTA)(PA)] system in Fig. 7. From the values of pL at $\bar{n}=0.5$, $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ can be calcu-

Fig. 6. Formation curves for [Pr(III)-(NTA)(PA)] system.

—○—○—○—25°
 —△—△—△—35°
 —●—●—●—45°

lated. These values have been further refined by using the method of interpolation at various \bar{n} values. The values obtained are presented in Table 1.

Fig 7 Formation curves for [Pr(III)-(HEDTA)(PA)] system.

—○—○—○— 25°
—△—△—△— 35°
—●—●—●— 45°

Discussion

An observation of the values of first step formation constants of Pr(III) complexes with the ligands used shows the order of complex stability constants (K_{ML}) is NRS > PA. The order is in accordance with the basicities of the ligands. In both the cases, stabilities of complexes are found in decreasing order with increasing temperature. Both the ligands act as bidentate. Co-ordination in case of PA takes place through nitrogen atom of pyridine ring and the carboxyl group⁹ and in case NRS complexation is through the oxime group (-NOH). The possibility of H-bonding in complexes of this kind cannot be ruled out but must be confirmed by more detailed studies on related systems.

An observation of ternary systems shows that the formation constants with same secondary ligand and different primary ligands is in the order of $K_{ML}^{NTA} > K_{ML}^{HEDTA} > K_{ML}^{EDTA}$. It can be explained on the basis that lesser number of co-ordination positions will be available for secondary ligand in case of EDTA, than with HEDTA, than with NTA system. It is obvious from the results tabulated above that the stability of corresponding binary chelates are

higher than the ternary chelates (K_{ML}) > (K_{ML}^{ML}). In case of binary systems the ligands (L) has to approach positively charged Pr(III) ion and more room is available for its co-ordination, whereas in case of ternary complexes it has to overcome the electrostatic forces and less positions are available for its co-ordination, which results in lowering the stability of these chelates. The secondary ligands PA and NRS act as bidentate while the primary ligands NTA, HEDTA and EDTA act as tetra, penta and hexadentate respectively with Pr(III). In the mixed-ligand chelates using NTA as primary ligands the total co-ordination number of six is satisfied (four with NTA and two with the PA or NRS). The formation of mixed-ligand chelates using HEDTA or EDTA as primary ligands, two different mechanisms may be proposed.

(i) Pr(III) ion does not increase its co-ordination number greater than six and hence to accommodate an incoming bidentate secondary ligand (PA or NRS), one or two weakly co-ordinated group of HEDTA and EDTA respectively are displaced, thus making them to act as tetradentate. The net result is that in the mixed-ligand system the co-ordination number of Pr(III) remains as six.

(ii) The Pr(III) increases its co-ordination number greater than six to accommodate the bidentate secondary ligand and thus co-ordination number of Pr(III) expands to seven or eight in case of mixed-ligand complexes of HEDTA and EDTA respectively.

On the basis of experimental evidence collected in the present study, it is possible to make positive suggestions in favour of second mechanism, i.e., on the expansion of co-ordination number of Pr(III).

It has been reported earlier that Pr(III)-(HEDTA) and Pr(III)-(EDTA) primary complexes start hydrolysing at $pH \approx 8.5$ and 9.0 respectively. In case of mixed-ligand system reported here, it is found that the pH of hydrolysis shifts to about 10.5 in both the cases. It is only possible if an expansion of co-ordination number of Pr(III) is considered. Otherwise how does the pH of hydrolysis of these mixed-ligand chelates increases? Thus, the co-ordination number of Pr(III) expands to seven and eight in the mixed-ligand chelates of HEDTA and EDTA respectively when a secondary bidentate ligand like PA or NRS attaches itself to the primary complex.

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